

sulphide. This view gains support from the fact that the absorption bands shown by polyphenylene ethers also correspond to those observed for diphenyl ether (λ_{\max} 279, 272, 227 nm; ϵ_{\max} 1 800, 2 000, 9 300, respectively Table 3). The two low intensity bands at 279 and 272 nm correspond to the vibrational bands of the benzenoid spectrum and their positions remain remarkably unchanged. The more intense shortwave band (227–243 nm) is due to oxygen-benzene conjugation. This is seen to undergo a small bathochromic shift as the length of the molecule increases. A striking resemblance exists between this band and the shorter wavelength band of diphenyl sulphide, both arising from the same type of conjugation. The second band seen for sulphides is not seen for oxygen compounds, as *d*-orbital resonance is not possible for the latter.

An interesting feature of the spectral data (Table 3) is that for each of the conjugation bands the ratio of ϵ_{\max} to the number of sulphur or oxygen atoms present in the molecule is almost constant. This principle is not applicable to the vibrational bands of benzene. It is also not applicable to *m*-diphenylthiobenzene and *m*-diphenoxybenzene.

While a regularity is found in the increase of λ_{\max} and ϵ_{\max} for parapolyphenylene ethers and sulphides as the chainlength increases (S or O from 2 to 4), the same regularity is not found as we move from the first member of each series to the next member. This may be due to the presence of $-\text{S}-\text{C}_6\text{H}_4-\text{S}-$ or $-\text{O}-\text{C}_6\text{H}_4-\text{O}-$ unit in the polyphenylene compounds and its absence in the first member of the series.

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Reaction of Steroidal Epoxide with Nitriles

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A number of oxazoline derivatives have been found to possess various biological activities¹ and a multidirectional applicability in several industries². Hence, an attempt has been made to synthesise the steroidal oxazoline from steroidal epoxide by a simple method. The configuration of oxazoline ring in **2** has been confirmed by ¹H nmr and also by its drying model.

Scheme 1. Reagents: (a) PhCN, BF₃-etherate, 25°,
(b) CH₃CN, BF₃-etherate, 25°

Scheme 2

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL AND SPECTRAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS 2–5*

Compd. no.	Mol. formula	Solvent of elution (Pet. ether-ether)	M.p.** °C	Yield %	ν_{\max} cm ⁻¹	δ †	m/z
2	C ₂₄ H ₄₈ N ₂ O ₂	20 : 1	68 ^a	56.6	1 680 (C=N), 1 620 (C=C), 1 600, 1 590 (C=C, aromatic), 1 520, 1 375 (C-NO ₂), 1 062 (C-O-C)	7.9–7.5 (5H, m, ArH), 4.9 (1H, d, <i>J</i> 4 Hz, C4 β -H), 3.75 (1H, m, W _{1/2} 7.5 Hz, C3 β -H) ^c	532 (M ⁺), 515 (M ⁺ -OH), 486 (M ⁺ -NO ₂), 485 (M ⁺ -HNO ₂), 119 (C ₇ H ₅ NO), 77 (C ₆ H ₅)
3	C ₂₄ H ₄₈ N ₂ O ₂	5 : 1	146 ^a	26.6	3 270 (NH), 1 655 (amide I), 1 622 (C=C), 1 605, 1 595 (C=C, aromatic), 1 510 (amide II), 1 525, 1 370 (C-NO ₂)	7.7–7.5 (5H, m, ArH), 7.1 (1H, brs, exchangeable with deuterium, C4-NH-CO-), 6.0 (1H, unresolved m, W _{1/2} 5 Hz, C ₂ -vinylic proton)	532 (M ⁺), 486 (M ⁺ -NO ₂), 455 (M ⁺ -C ₆ H ₅), 105 (C ₆ H ₅ CO), 77 (C ₆ H ₅)
4	C ₂₇ H ₄₈ N ₂ O ₂	20 : 1	167 ^b	18.6	3 420 (OH), 3 380 (NH ₂), 1 620 (C=C), 1 520, 1 375 (C-NO ₂), 1 045 (C-N)	4.28 (1H, m, W _{1/2} 7.5 Hz, C3 β -H) ^c , 4.0 (1H, dist d, <i>J</i> 3.5 Hz, C4 α -H), 2.4 (2H, mc, exchangeable with deuterium, C4-NH ₂), 1.74 (1H, brs, exchangeable with deuterium, C3-OH)	446 (M ⁺), 431 (M ⁺ -CH ₃), 430 (M ⁺ -NH ₂), 429 (M ⁺ -NH ₂), 428 (M ⁺ -H ₂ O), 400 (M ⁺ -NO ₂)
5	C ₂₆ H ₄₈ N ₂ O ₄	8 : 1	213 ^b	53.3	3 560 (OH), 3 430 (NH), 1 655 (amide I), 1 620 (C=C), 1 510 (amide II), 1 520, 1 385 (C-NO ₂)	5.5 (1H, brs, exchangeable with deuterium, C4-NH-CO-), 4.48 (1H, d, <i>J</i> 3.6 Hz, C4 α -H), 4.11 (mc, W _{1/2} 7 Hz, C3 β -H) ^c , 2.0 (3H, s, C4-CH ₃ -CO-), 1.7 (1H, brs, exchangeable with deuterium, C3-OH)	488 (M ⁺), 470 (M ⁺ -H ₂ O), 446 (M ⁺ -CH ₃ =C=O), 442 (M ⁺ -NO ₂)

*All compounds gave satisfactory C, H and N analyses. **Solvent for crystallisation : ^aPetroleum ether, ^bmethanol. † Angular and side-chain methyl protons appeared at δ 1.28–0.70 : ^cRef. 4.

Experimental

All melting points are uncorrected. Ir spectra (KBr/nujol) were determined on a Pye-Unicam SP3-100 spectrophotometer, ¹H nmr spectra (CDCl₃) on a Varian A 60D instrument with Me₄Si as the internal standard and mass spectra on a JeOL-D 300 spectrometer at 70 eV.

Reaction of 3 α , 4 α -epoxy-6-nitrocholest-5-ene (1) with benzonitrile : Boron trifluoride-etherate (2 ml) was added dropwise (15 min) to a stirred suspension of the epoxide³ (1; 3.0 g) in benzonitrile (20 ml) at room temperature. The resulting solution was further stirred for 20 min and then poured into aqueous sodium bicarbonate solution (5%) and extracted with dichloromethane. The extract was washed with water and dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate. Removal of the solvent gave an oil which was chromatographed over silica gel (30 g).

Reaction of 3 α , 4 α -epoxy-6-nitrocholest-5-ene (1) with acetonitrile : Reaction of the epoxide (1; 3.0 g) with acetonitrile (20 ml) was performed as described in earlier in the presence of boron trifluoride-etherate (2 ml). After usual work up of the reaction mixture and removal of the solvent, an oily residue was

obtained which was chromatographed over silica gel (40 g). Elution with petroleum ether-ether at different solvent ratios gave different products (Table 1).

This simple method of preparation of steroidal oxazoline, amine and amido derivatives in high yield may be used for the synthesis of such type of compounds which may exhibit some interesting biological activities.

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Organoinsecticide Synergists. Part-I. Synthesis of Substituted-benzyl-2-propynyl Ethers and their Synergistic Activity

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A number of ring substituted benzyl 2-propynyl ethers (3a-1) were synthesised and tested for synergistic activity with mobam and supracide insecticides against house flies. The structures of synergist candidates were confirmed on the basis of elemental analysis, ir and nmr studies.

In the field of pesticide chemistry, a number of publications and dissertations have dealt with the synergistic activity of compounds containing the acetylenic group¹⁻³. Gibbons reported² that certain benzyl 2-propynyl ethers were effective as carbamate and organo phosphorous synergists. But very little work has been done on the structure-activity relationships of benzyl 2-propynyl ethers. In the present investigation, we have, therefore, carried out the synthesis of a large number of hitherto unreported benzyl 2-propynyl ethers and studied their synergistic activity. The synthetic steps involved to prepare ring substituted benzyl 2-propynyl ethers are outlined in Scheme 1. The benzyl bromides

(2) were prepared by heating appropriately substituted-toluenes either with NBS in the presence of light and benzyl peroxide as a catalyst or with bromine in carbon tetrachloride in the presence of light. The benzyl 2-propynyl ethers (3a-1) were prepared⁴ by the reaction of the appropriate benzyl bromides (2) with sodium propargylate in propargyl alcohol. Their structures were determined by ir and nmr spectral data. The compounds (3a-1) were screened for their synergistic activity with supracide or mobam against resistant female house flies, employing the Topical Application method⁶.

Biological activity: The results reveal that the presence of NO₂, CN and Br groups in *ortho*-position of the phenyl ring of compounds 3 enhanced the activity whereas substitution with acetyl, methyl and t-butyl groups resulted low activity. Dichloro derivatives appeared to be more active than the monochloro derivatives. Bromo derivatives were found to be good synergists for supracide. The most active candidates (100% 24 h mortality with supracide insecticide) were the 2,6-dichloro, 2-chloro-6-fluoro, 2-chloro-6-nitro, 2-chloro-6-cyano and 2-nitro-6-methyl derivatives.

Experimental

¹H Nmr spectra (CDCl₃) were determined on a Varian A-60A (60 MHz) spectrometer using TMS as an internal standard and ir spectra (CCl₄) on a Perkin-Elmer 137 spectrophotometer. Melting points were determined on a Fischer-Johns apparatus and are uncorrected. Elemental analysis were performed at Schwarzkopf Microanalytical Laboratory, Woodside, New York, U.S.A.

General method for preparation of benzylbromides (2). *Method A: Preparation of 2a-j:* To a solution of appropriately substituted toluene (0.1 mol) in carbon tetrachloride (150 ml) were added *N*-bromosuccinimide (19.6 g, 0.11 mol) and benzoylperoxide (1g) as a catalyst. The reaction mixture was stirred well and during the reaction two 150W lamps were focussed upon the reaction flask, which caused the reaction mixture to reflux. After completion of the reaction, as shown by rising of the formed succinimide to the top of the solution, the reaction mixture was cooled and filtered. The filtrate was first washed with 10% sodium bisulphite solution (100 ml), then with water, dried and concentrated under reduced pressure. The residue (if oily liquid) was either (if liquid) fractionally distilled at reduced pressure or crystallised (if solid) from suitable solvent.

Method B: Preparation of 2k-1: To a solution of appropriately substituted toluene (0.1 mol) in carbon tetrachloride (300 ml), bromine (19.2 g, 0.12 mol) was added slowly over a period of 6 h. The reaction mixture was further refluxed until the evolution of HBr gas eventually stopped. It was then cooled, washed with 10% sodium bisulphite solution (100 ml), then with water, dried and concentrated under reduced pressure. The crude residue

Scheme 1

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